

MILITARY VOCABULARY IN BUSINESS ENGLISH

Karimova Diyora Abduvaxidovna,

Tashkent University of Information Technologies

named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

Department of foreign languages

E-mail: diyora.karimova.87@mail.ru

Abstract: *The business world is full of military idioms and expressions. For many people, business is war. Just think about how many English verbs related to the military theme used in business English. Defend one's position in the market (defend your position in the market): capture a larger slice of the market (grab a big jackpot in the market); reinforce position (strengthen positions). Phraseological composition, nationally specific in nature, serves to preserve and transmit experience of native speakers of an ethnic community, their cultural and historical heritage, moral and ethical attitudes and values.*

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Phraseological units reflect the worldview of a person and people, due to which exist in the language not only to describe objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality, but also to expressions of a subjective attitude towards them, which is manifested in such a property of phraseology as anthropocentricity. The idea of a direct connection between language and man is now generally accepted. A significant part of the dictionary of any language is devoted to a person - his activity, inner world, perception surrounding reality, assessment of events and phenomena, relationships with other people. Phraseologisms of military subjects often have a connotation of positive or negative assessment, which can be expressed explicitly, which implies the presence of an evaluative word directly. As part of a phraseological unit (an expression an awkward squad - a platoon of recruits, "clumsy platoon") and implicitly. An implication is a meaning that is guessed by the carrier, but not verbally expressed: big brass –generals, generals, high-ranking military, high authorities; heavy metal is a dangerous opponent; old mustache - veteran, seasoned soldier. Set phrases of the military sphere are used in the language to describe and evaluate such qualities human personality, of paramount importance in terms of military service, as courage, strength will, camaraderie, determination. Along with them, there are phraseological units that

have pejorative coloring, which express deceit, cowardice, indecision, stupidity.

One of the main positive qualities inherent in a real warrior is willpower, about which evidenced by a large number of phraseological units representing this stereotype in the culture of the English-speaking peoples:

fight one's battles over again - stand up for yourself, cope with difficulties yourself;

draw the sword and throw away the scabbard - "draw the sword and discard the scabbard", get ready for the most decisive action;

fight like a lion - fight like a lion. The ability of a person in any conditions and under any circumstances to achieve goals, firmly and unwaveringly fulfill their duty to the motherland and courageously endure all the hardships and hardships of military service at all times were the dominants of army culture. These qualities are reflected in the following phraseological units: show fight - be ready to fight, be militant, do not give up; continue resistance;

stand to one's guns - do not give up positions, hold on steadfastly, firmly, stand your ground, withstand character (this. military. do not throw guns);

stand fire - withstand criticism, resist difficulties;

military stand fire;

draw fire from smb. - become the target of attacks, ridicule; military cause fire on yourself;

bear the brunt of smth. - bear the brunt of something (military. take the main blow of the enemy);

attack is the best method of defense - the best defense is an attack.

Another important component of a positive image of a soldier is his devotion traditions of military camaraderie. Relationships in the military team that affect its cohesion and combat readiness, served as the foundation for the emergence of the following phraseological units:

fling (throw) oneself into the breach - help out of trouble, come to the rescue;

fight smb.'s battles (for him) - fight for someone's cause, stand up for someone;

strike a blow for smb. (smth.) - to speak in defense of someone (something);

companion (comrade) in arms - comrade in arms, comrade-in-arms, comrade-in-arms;

brother in arms - brother in arms;

two is one and one is none (you need a backup to be sure) - one in the field is not a warrior

Business requires a strong strategy for those who want to succeed (succeed), so you need to think strategically (think strategically) to win the battle (win the battle). Be on the defensive is not the best option. Sometimes aggressive moves are required. The listed phrases are commonly used by both native speakers and other businessmen at business meetings and in correspondence. Business magazines and the media are filled with these phrases. If your business communication in English does not bring the desired results, you should stock up on the following military idioms with explanation and examples, which we have selected specifically for those who fight not on the battlefield, but in offices.

1. Take (the) flak, which means "to be strongly criticized or attacked." it is a hail of bullets aimed at an enemy aircraft from the ground.

- The marketing department will take the flak for wrong policy that didn't result in sales boost. - the marketing department will be sharply criticized for the wrong policy that did not lead to sales growth

2. Set your sights on aim at something, set a goal in front of you. During hostilities, a target is aimed at the enemy before firing.

- Do you set your sights on concluding a new contract by the end of this year? Are you aiming to sign a new contract by the end of this year?

3. A minefield - (minefield) refers to a situation that is complicated by hidden threats and problems.

- Adopting your option means entering a minefield. - if we accept your offer, we will incur many problems

4. Lay low - in war, soldiers often lay low (lie down on the ground) to wait, watch the enemy, before going on the attack. In the business world, this phrase means "to wait before doing anything"

- I suggest to lay low and see what will our rivals do. I suggest we wait and see what our competitors do.

5. Give up without a fight

- I know Tom. He will never give up without a fight I know Tom. He just won't give up.

- I am not going to give my position up without a fight

6. Lose ground - retreat, lose positions.

- If we lose time we will lose ground against our rivals

7. To be your own worst enemy "to cut the branch on which you sit", "to your own enemy" in this situation, problems arise due to their own character and shortcomings.

• I can't understand you. You are your own enemy! How could you refuse the position of a managing director? - I don't understand you, you're your own enemy. How could you turn down the position of managing director?

8. Casualties - "losses, victims" are those who died or were wounded in the war, and outside the war they are people who suffered from something that happened for reasons beyond their control.

• Pensioners are always the first casualty in government reforms

9. Take no prisoners When they are not taken prisoner, they are killed on the spot, which means that this phrase means "to be ruthless.

• Our boss takes no prisoners in business, so do your best to satisfy his requirements - our boss does not know pity in business, so try to fulfill his requirements.

10. Make a killing

• Nobody knows what he made a killing on but today he owns a shipping company. •

No one knows what he profited from, but today he owns a shipping company.

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